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COMPARATIVE PHARMACOGNOSTICAL EVALUATION OF MARKET SAMPLE OF PANCHAVALKALA CHURNA

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Abstract

Background: *Panchavalkala* is one of the important herbal formulations of ayurveda. It is the combination of stem bark of five different plants: *Parish* (*Thespesia populnea* Soland.), *Ashvattha* (*Ficus religiosa* Linn.), *Nyagrodha* (*Ficus bengalensis* Linn.), *Udumbara* (*Ficus racemosa* Linn.) and *Plaksha* (*Ficus tsiela* Roxb.). To ensure the therapeutic efficacy and safety of herbal formulations and to justify their use in healthcare, standardization of these formulations is a crucial and necessary.

Material & Method: Powder microscopy of *Panchavalkala Churna* procured from the market of Vadodara, Gujarat, India was carried out. Slides of *Panchavalkala Churna* were prepared using the required reagent and observed under the microscope.

Observation & Result: Powder microscopy of *Panchavalkala Churna* shows the presence of Cork cells, Stone cells, Sclereids, Prismatic crystals of Calcium oxalates, Fibre fragments, Dark brown content, Starch grains, Phloem parenchyma, Laticiferous canal, etc.

Discussion and Conclusion: The microscopic features which were observed in the *Panchavalkala Churna* procured from the market revealed that it contains *Ashvatta* (*Ficus religiosa* Linn.), *Nyagrodha* (*Ficus benghalensis* Linn.), *Udumbara* (*Ficus racemosa* Linn.) (*Ficus racemosa* Linn.) and *Plaksha* (*Ficus tsiela* Roxb.). The absence of Rosette Crystals of Calcium oxalates, Cluster crystals of Calcium oxalate, brown coloured granular masses suggests that this sample does not contain *Parisha* (*Thespesia populnea* Soland. ex. Correa) as its ingredient.

Key Words:

Panchavalkala, Powder microscopy, *Ashvatta* (*Ficus religiosa* Linn.), *Nyagrodha* (*Ficus benghalensis* Linn.), *Udumbara* (*Ficus racemosa* Linn.), *Plaksha* (*Ficus tsiela* Roxb.), *Parisha* (*Thespesia populnea*

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INTRODUCTION:

The demand for medicinal plants used to make Ayurvedic medicines in India is far greater than the supply. Due to the growing demand for raw materials and the scarcity of resources, many manufacturers are forced to use adulterants and substitutes, which produces inferior products. The final product quality varies from pharmacy to pharmacy, and the production of herbal medications is inconsistent from batch to batch. Therefore, it is essential to ensure the therapeutic efficacy and safety of herbal formulations and to justify their use in healthcare, standardization of these formulations.

For the present study, one of the most important herbal formulations of ayurveda, *Panchavalkala* is selected. *Panchavalkala* is a group of drugs which is referred to stem bark of five plants. It consists of *Ashvatta* (*Ficus religiosa* Linn.), *Nyagrodha* (*Ficus benghalensis* Linn.), *Udumbara* (*Ficus racemosa* Linn.), *Plaksha* (*Ficus tsiela* Roxb.) and *Parisha* (*Thespesia populnea* Soland. ex. Correa)¹. This herbal formulation is widely used externally in range of disorders like gynaecological disorders, for wound healing, skin diseases, etc. So, to ensure the quality and standards of the sample of *Panchavalkala Churna* procured from the market, along with the identification of characteristic feature of each ingredient of the combination in the sample, which enables us to identify the presence or absence of any adulterant and contaminant in the market sample.

AIM:

To study the powder microscopic features of *Panchavalkala Churna* procured from the market of Vadodara, Gujarat, India.

OBJECTIVE:

1. To study the powder microscopic features of *Panchavalkala Churna* procured from the market of Vadodara, Gujarat, India
2. To compare the assessed features of the *Panchavalkala Churna* formulation with their standards of each of the individual ingredient mentioned in authentic reference.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The sample of *Panchavalkala Churna* was procured from the market of Vadodara, Gujarat, India in the month of October 2024. The study was performed at Pharmacognosy Laboratory of Upgraded Department of Dravyaguna Vijnana, Government Ayurved College, Vadodara, Gujarat.

Slide preparation:

Slide of *Panchavalkala Churna* procured from the market was prepared using required reagent and observed under

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the microscope to assess their various microscopic features. Microscopic characters observed were compared with the standards mentioned in authentic reference.

OBSERVATIONS & DISCUSSION:

Table No. 1: Powder Microscopic features of *Panchavalkala Churna* found in Market Sample

Sr. no.	Microscopic features	<i>Ashvatta (Ficus religiosa Linn.)</i>	<i>Nyagrodha (Ficus benghalensis Linn.)</i>	<i>Udumbara (Ficus racemosa Linn.)</i>	<i>Plaksha (Ficus tsiela Roxb.)</i>	<i>Parisha (Thespesia populnea Soland. ex. Correa)</i>
1.	Cork cells	+	+	+	-	+
2.	Stone cells	+	+	+	+	-
3.	Sclereids	+	+	-	+	+
4.	Prismatic crystals of Calcium oxalates	+	+	+	+	-
5.	Fibre fragments	+	+	+	+	+
6.	Dark brown content	+	-	-	-	-
7.	Starch grains	+	+	+	+	+
8.	Phloem parenchyma	+	+	+	+	-
9.	Laticiferous canal	-	+	+	+	-
10.	Tannin cells	-	+	-	-	-
11.	Yellowish brown content	-	-	+	+	-
12.	Pitted parenchyma	-	-	-	+	-

- Absent, + Present

Table No. 2: Microscopic features in authentic reference² compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Ashvatta (Ficus religiosa Linn.)* found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Ashvatta (Ficus religiosa Linn.)</i> in authentic reference	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Stone cells	+	[Fig. 1.a]

2.	Starch grains	+	[Fig. 1.b]
3.	Sclereids	+	[Fig. 1.c]
4.	Prismatic crystals of Calcium oxalates	+	[Fig. 1.d]
5.	Cork cells	+	[Fig. 1.e]
6.	Dark brown content	+	[Fig. 1.f]
7.	Fibre fragments	+	[Fig. 1.f]
8.	Phloem parenchyma	+	[Fig. 1.g]

- Absent, + Present

Table No. 3: Microscopic features in authentic reference³ compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Nyagrodha (Ficus benghalensis Linn.)* found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Nyagrodha (Ficus benghalensis Linn.)</i> in authentic reference	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Cork cells	+	[Fig. 2.a]
2.	Tannin cells	+	[Fig. 2.b]
3.	Starch grains	+	[Fig. 2.c]
4.	Sclereids	+	[Fig. 2.d]
5.	Prismatic crystals of Calcium oxalate	+	[Fig. 2.e]
6.	Phloem parenchyma	+	[Fig. 2.f]
7.	Fibre fragments	+	[Fig. 2.g]
8.	Laticiferous canal	+	[Fig. 2.h]
9.	Stone cells	+	[Fig. 2.h]

- Absent, + Present

Table No. 4: Microscopic features in authentic reference⁴ compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Udumbara (Ficus racemosa Linn.)* found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Udumbara (Ficus racemosa Linn.)</i> in authentic reference	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
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1.	Stone cells	+	[Fig. 3.a]
2.	Phloem parenchyma	+	[Fig. 3.b]
3.	Prismatic crystal	+	[Fig. 3.b]
4.	Cork cells	+	[Fig. 3.c]
5.	Fibre fragments	+	[Fig. 3.d]
6.	Laticiferous canal	+	[Fig. 3.e]
7.	Starch grains	+	[Fig. 3.f]
8.	Yellowish brown content	+	[Fig. 3.g]

- Absent, + Present

Table No. 5: Microscopic features in authentic reference⁵ compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Plaksha (Ficus tsiela Roxb.)* found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Plaksha (Ficus tsiela Roxb.)</i> in authentic reference	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Prismatic crystals of Calcium oxalates	+	[Fig. 4.a]
2.	Stone cells	+	[Fig. 4.b] [Fig. 4.e]
3.	Laticiferous canal	+	[Fig. 4.b]
4.	Fibre fragments	+	[Fig. 4.c]
5.	Stone cells filled with yellowish brown content	+	[Fig. 4.c]
6.	Starch grains	+	[Fig. 4.d]
7.	Sclerosed medullary rays	+	[Fig. 4.e]
8.	Pitted phloem parenchyma	+	[Fig. 4.f]
9.	Cork cells	+	[Fig. 4.g]
10.	Pitted parenchyma	+	[Fig. 4.h]

- Absent, + Present

Table No. 6: Microscopic features in authentic reference⁶ compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Parisha* (*Thespesia populnea* Soland. ex. Correa) found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Parisha</i> (<i>Thespesia populnea</i> Soland. ex. Correa) in authentic reference	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Fibre fragment	+	[Fig. 5.a]
2.	Starch grains	+	[Fig. 5.b]
3.	Sclereids	+	[Fig. 5.c]
4.	Cork cells	+	[Fig. 5.d]
5.	Brown coloured granular mass	-	-
6.	Rosette crystals of Calcium oxalates	-	-
7.	Cluster crystals of Calcium oxalates	-	-
8.	Secretory canal	-	-

- Absent, + Present

Through this present study information regarding the microscopic characters of the herbal formulation procured from the market can be known. For this microscopic study, powder of *Panchavalkala Churna* was selected. The powder microscopic characters of *Panchavalkala* were observed which will be narrated further. Powder microscopy of *Panchavalkala Churna* shows, presence of Stone cells, Starch grains, Sclereids, Prismatic crystals of Calcium oxalates, Cork cells, Dark brown content, Fibre fragments and Phloem parenchyma suggests that it contains *Ashvatta* (*Ficus religiosa* Linn.); presence of Cork cells, Tannin cells, Starch grains, Sclereids, Prismatic crystals of Calcium oxalate, Phloem parenchyma, Fibre fragments, Laticiferous canal and Stone cells suggests that it contains *Nyagrodha* (*Ficus benghalensis* Linn.); presence of Stone cells, Phloem parenchyma, Prismatic crystal, Cork cells, Fibre fragments, Laticiferous canal, Starch grains and Yellowish brown content suggests it contains *Udumbara* (*Ficus racemosa* Linn.); and presence of Prismatic crystals of Calcium oxalates, Stone cells, Laticiferous canal, Fibre fragments, Stone cells filled with yellowish brown content, Starch grains, Sclerosed medullary rays, Pitted phloem parenchyma and Pitted parenchyma suggests it contains *Plaksha* (*Ficus tsiela* Roxb.). But in these sample, absence of Rosette crystals of Calcium oxalate, Cluster crystals of Calcium oxalate, secretory canal and brown coloured granular mass which are the key identification characteristics of *Parisha* (*Thespesia populnea* Soland. ex. Correa) are absent. These suggests that it does not contain *Parisha* (*Thespesia populnea* Soland. ex. Correa) as its ingredients.

CONCLUSION:

Stem bark of *Ashvatta* (*Ficus religiosa* Linn.), *Nyagrodha* (*Ficus benghalensis* Linn.), *Udumbara* (*Ficus racemosa* Linn.), *Plaksha* (*Ficus tsiela* Roxb.) and *Parisha* (*Thespesia populnea* Soland. ex. Correa) are included in *Panchavalkala* compound.

Key identifications of features of Stem bark of *Ashvatta* (*Ficus religiosa* Linn.), *Nyagrodha* (*Ficus benghalensis* Linn.), *Udumbara* (*Ficus racemosa* Linn.), *Plaksha* (*Ficus tsiela* Roxb.) and *Parisha* (*Thespesia populnea* Soland. ex. Correa):

Sr. no.	Plant	Key identification features
1.	<i>Ashvatta</i> (<i>Ficus religiosa</i> Linn.)	Stone cells, starch grains, prismatic crystals of Calcium oxalates and dark brown content
2.	<i>Nyagrodha</i> (<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> Linn.)	Stone cells, starch grains, prismatic crystals of Calcium oxalates, tannin cells and laticiferous canal
3.	<i>Udumbara</i> (<i>Ficus racemosa</i> Linn.)	Stone cells, starch grains, prismatic crystals of Calcium oxalates, laticiferous canal and yellowish-brown content
4.	<i>Plaksha</i> (<i>Ficus tsiela</i> Roxb.)	Stone cells, stone cells filled with yellowish brown content, prismatic crystals of Calcium oxalates, and sclerosed medullary rays
5.	<i>Parisha</i> (<i>Thespesia populnea</i> Soland. ex. Correa)	Rosette crystals of Calcium oxalates, cluster crystals of Calcium oxalates, secretory canal and brown coloured granular mass

The market sample procured from the markets of Vadodara, Gujarat, India, contains *Ashvatta* (*Ficus religiosa* Linn.), *Nyagrodha* (*Ficus benghalensis* Linn.), *Udumbara* (*Ficus racemosa* Linn.) and *Plaksha* (*Ficus tsiela* Roxb.), but the key identification features of *Parisha* (*Thespesia populnea* Soland. ex. Correa) were absent, thus it suggests that it does not contain *Parisha* (*Thespesia populnea* Soland. ex. Correa).

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Plate No. 1: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Panchavalka Churna – Ashvatta (Ficus religiosa Linn.)*

Fig. 1(a). Stone cells

Fig. 1(b). Starch Grains

Fig. 1(c). Sclereids

Fig. 1(d). Prismatic crystal

Fig. 1(e). Pitted cork cell

Fig. 1(f). Fibre fragment

Fig. 1(g). Phloem Parenchyma

Plate No. 2: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Panchavalka Churna* – Nyagodha

Fig. 2(a). Cork cells

Fig. 2(b). Tannin cells

Fig. 2(c). Starch grains

Fig. 2(d). Sclereids

Fig. 2(e). Prismatic Crystals

Fig. 2(f). Phloem parenchyma

Fig. 2(g). Fibre fragment

Fig. 2(h). stone cells with laticiferous canal

Plate No. 3: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Panchavalka Churna* – *Udumbara* (*Ficus racemosa* Linn.)

Fig. 3(a). Stone cells

Fig. 3(b) phloem parenchyma and prismatic crystal

Fig. 3(c). Cork cells

Fig. 3(d). fibre fragment

Fig. 3(e). Laticiferous canal

Fig. 3(f). Starch grains

Fig. 3(g). Yellowish brown content

Plate No. 4: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Panchavalka Churna – Plaksha (Ficus tsiela Roxb.)*

Fig. 4(a). Prismatic Crystal

Fig. 4(b). Stone cells and laticiferous canal

Fig. 4(c). fibre fragment and stone cells filled with yellowish brown content

Fig. 4(d). Starch grains

Fig. 4(e). Stone cells and sclerosed medullary rays

Fig. 4(f). Pitted parenchyma

Fig. 4(g). Cork cells

Fig. 4(h). pitted phloem parenchyma

Plate No. 5: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Panchavalkala Churna – Parisha (Thespesia populnea Soland. ex. Correa)*

Fig. 5(a). Fibre fragment

Fig. 5(b). cells containing Starch grains

Fig. 5(c). Sclereids

Fig. 5(d). Cork Cells

REFERENCES

1. Hegde Prakash L, Harini A. A Textbook of Dravyaguna Vijnana Vol I, New Delhi; Chaukhambha Publications. 2016; p 426-427.
2. Malati G. Chauhan, A. P. G. Pillai. Microscopic Profile of powdered drugs used in Indian Systems of Medicine Vol 1, Jamnagar; Institute of Ayurvedic Medicinal Plant Sciences. 2004; p 22-23.
3. Malati G. Chauhan, A. P. G. Pillai. Microscopic Profile of powdered drugs used in Indian Systems of Medicine Vol 1, Jamnagar; Institute of Ayurvedic Medicinal Plant Sciences. 2004; p 74-75
4. Malati G. Chauhan, A. P. G. Pillai. Microscopic Profile of powdered drugs used in Indian Systems of Medicine Vol 1, Jamnagar; Institute of Ayurvedic Medicinal Plant Sciences. 2004; p 108-109.

5. Malati G. Chauhan, A. P. G. Pillai. Microscopic Profile of powdered drugs used in Indian Systems of Medicine Vol 1, Jamnagar; Institute of Ayurvedic Medicinal Plant Sciences. 2004; p 82-83
6. Malati G. Chauhan, A. P. G. Pillai. Microscopic Profile of powdered drugs used in Indian Systems of Medicine Vol 1, Jamnagar; Institute of Ayurvedic Medicinal Plant Sciences. 2004; p 78-79.

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